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The Rice Knowledge Bank at IRRI: Strengthening Training Capacity¹

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The fast and effective transfer of technologies from the research laboratory to the farmer's field has always been one of the biggest challenges facing those in agricultural development. All too often, new technologies are successfully developed only to fail in reaching those who need them most—the farmers—because of inadequate or underdeveloped government extension services. This unfortunate situation is made worse when the new technologies are neglected and forgotten because they are not used. Nongovernment organizations (NGOs) have started to play an important role in the area of extension, but most do not have the resources to develop their own technologies and must rely on access to institutes like IRRI to provide what they need.

Into this yawning gap between research and impact has stepped the Rice Knowledge Bank. Not only is it one of the world's first digital extension services for those who provide information and support for farmers (such as NGOs), it is also the first comprehensive, digital rice production library containing an ever-increasing wealth of information on training and rice production.

More importantly, it provides this service using a breakthrough format that sets a new standard for knowledge and information access within the agricultural development community. Taking the very latest and best ideas from the private sector's work in this area, the Rice Knowledge Bank is providing government extension officers, NGOs, and all others interested with unprecedented access to rice knowledge and training information.

¹The entire contents of this article may be accessed as an eBook by pointing your browser to <http://www.knowledgebank.irri.org/rkb>.

The world's rice knowledge repository... freely sharing knowledge.

Background and purpose

First and foremost, IRRI is a rice science and research institute. However, IRRI's founders knew that, to get the science and research out of the laboratory and into farmers' fields, there had to be an educational component. This belief manifests itself on the bronze plaque in front of the headquarters building, "IRRI ... an educational and research institute." Therefore, education and training are seen as the conduit through which IRRI's science becomes practice, the kind of practice that ensures that farmers can continue to grow more rice on less land, with fewer chemical inputs and that the world's rice-consuming poor will continue to have an adequate food supply.

Over the past 40 years, IRRI training has pushed a variety of instructional methodologies and technologies through the *conduit*. Printed materials, photographic slide-audio tape modules, instructional video, early attempts at computer-aided instruction, video-conferencing, and information presented on stand-alone CD-ROM have supported face-to-face classroom instruction, in-country and

in-field (hands-on) training, and scholar and partnership development.

Now, IRRI training is developing and adding another set of tools to its training toolbox: those that are collectively known as information and communication technology (ICT), which include distance learning and the Internet. The Rice Knowledge Bank is the physical manifestation of this development and, since its official launch in September 2002 at the International Rice Congress in Beijing, China, it has received critical acclaim and provided "thought leadership" to the entire Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR) regarding the use of ICT.

The shift from atoms to bits

The Rice Knowledge Bank is more than just a way to deliver instructional content using ICT. For IRRI training, the Knowledge Bank is changing the very nature by which training materials are collected, organized, managed, published, and delivered. The best way to conceptualize this shift is to consider the nature of instructional materials as either *atom-based* or *bit-based*. Atom-based instructional materials are those that are composed of incompatible atoms, while bit-based materials are composed of compatible bits: the zeros and ones that form the basis of Internet-enabled ICT.

For example, print materials are the product of the atoms and compounds that create ink and

Digitizing existing atom-based learning materials and preparing new content using bit-based technologies ensure an Internet-compatible future.

paper, while photographs and video are the product of the atoms that create film. These formats are adequate but limited due to their atom-based structure. It is impossible to link a location within a printed document to a place in a videotape. Likewise, to find a piece of information within a set of printed documents requires an exhaustive search of the documents' indexes and tables of content. Moreover, if one audience required a printed version of the content, while another audience wanted to access the content via the Internet, conventional wisdom would suggest the creation of two separate versions.

In contrast, bit-based instructional technologies are *all* composed of zeros and ones. By converting legacy instructional materials to bit-based technologies and creating new materials in a digital format, the ability to link and cross-reference materials—whether they are video, print, or graphic—becomes a reality.

To explain this concept, Nicholas Negroponte² of the MIT Media Lab suggests the following:

The best way to appreciate the merits and consequences of being digital is to reflect on the dif-

ference between bits and atoms. While we are undoubtedly in an information age, most information is delivered to us in the form of atoms: videotape, newspapers, magazines, and books.

The information superhighway, on the other hand, is about the global movement of weightless bits at the speed of light. To get onto the superhighway, we must either produce content from the start in a bit-based digital form, or convert legacy atom-based content into 0's and 1's by using optical scanning and analog to digital conversion devices.

The rendering of information and media in digital form, combined with personal computing power and networks in everything from PCs to home appliances, allows computers to become full and active participants in all aspects of our lives.... The move from atoms to bits in the classroom will be a move from passivity to active participation and exploration.

The shift at IRRI is spearheaded by its Communication and Publications Services (CPS). Over the past 25 months, CPS has digitized 340 publica-

²Negroponte N. 1998. *The new engines of learning*. Exec. Educ. 17(1):25-27.

tions (approximately 70,550 pages), audited and classified more than 135,000 photographs and slides, and, from these, scanned and digitized more than 4,000. Using the fruits of CPS efforts, the Rice Knowledge Bank adds value to the digitized bits by brokering them into eLearning courses, reference materials, decision support tools, and databases.

Since these instructional materials are created in a bit-based format, their delivery via the Internet is a given. But what if a user does not have access to the Internet? This is where the power of bit-based instructional materials is most apparent. All content within the Rice Knowledge Bank is built on a concept known as single-source publishing. Simply put, single-source publishing allows the Knowledge Bank's content to be produced in whatever form is required by the audience requesting its materials. In other words, if a user has a computer but no Internet connectivity, the Knowledge Bank's content can be easily delivered via CD-ROM. If a user has no computer whatsoever, the Knowledge Bank's content can be printed from the digital source and delivered via mail. The point is, rather than having multiple versions of the same content in multiple delivery formats, all content is produced from a single source. This ensures that the information is always consistent and eases the task of updating content as the updating is always accomplished at one location.

Anatomy of the Rice Knowledge Bank

Content within the Rice Knowledge Bank is classified into six categories: (1) eLearning, (2) KnowledgeBytes, (3) reference materials, (4) field practices and diagnostic tools, (5) rice biological da-

tabases and geographic information systems (GIS) maps, and (6) training materials. Within each category, content is structured as reusable learning and information objects; meaning that objects contained within one category can be cross-referenced and shared with items from other categories. For example, while the Rice Grain Quality course is located within the eLearning category, it reuses multiple objects from the Bank, including the field practices and diagnostic tool *TropRice* and various reference materials.

To provide consistency and ease of use, all assets within the Knowledge Bank share a common navigation structure and color scheme. The colors chosen for the Rice Knowledge Bank are based on the four biodiversity colors of yellow, orange, green, and blue. These colors correspond to the sun, earth, plant life, and water. Since IRRI is an organization dedicated to preserving Earth's natural resources while growing more food on limited land using less water and less chemical inputs, the four biodiversity colors and their respective shades are a good basis for the Knowledge Bank's color scheme and are seen throughout the entire repository.

IRRI is known for its Rice Germplasm Bank: the largest repository of rice germplasm in the world, containing more than 120,000 species of rice and its genetic relatives. During the Knowledge Bank's conception, it was decided to use the analogy of the Rice Germplasm bank to describe the Knowledge Bank's functionality. Just as the germplasm bank contains different species of rice that can be crossed to create new varieties of rice, so too can the individual learning objects within the Knowledge Bank be used in different ways to create new understanding.

The Rice Knowledge Bank categories

Category	Description
eLearning	eLearning courses present structured content to the learner in a linear sequence on a specific topic. For example, the eLearning course <i>Rice Grain Quality</i> takes learners from basic knowledge and comprehension to higher levels of synthesis and application through the duration of its 42 lessons divided into seven separate learning modules. The Rice Knowledge Bank eLearning courses have a theoretical basis in Robert Gagne's <i>Conditions of Learning</i> and mirror best-in-class models used by leading private-sector eLearning providers.
KnowledgeBytes	A KnowledgeByte is a term that describes a specific topic in a concise manner using a popular perspective. For example, the KnowledgeByte <i>Golden Rice</i> provides users with a quick overview of golden rice without overloading them with details.

Category	Description
Reference materials	Using a book-chapter-page analogy that is enhanced with search and index capability, Knowledge Bank reference materials typically focus on a single subject and are designed to provide factual information concerning a specific topic within the subject. Reference guides are more informational than instructional, meaning that their content has not been structured to support sequenced learning and that they are not intended to be read from start to finish. Rather, they are designed to allow users to search for specific information by using the search field or by navigating the books, chapters, and pages that are displayed in the reference guides' navigation window.
Field practices and diagnostic tools	Just as the category's name implies, this group of tools provides decision support to farmers and extension workers by providing decision trees for diagnosis, such as those found in <i>RiceDoctor</i> , or field practices, such as those found in <i>TropRice</i> .
Rice biological databases and GIS maps	This category launches the International Rice Information System database, which is the rice implementation phase of the International Crop Information System (ICIS), which is a database that provides integrated management of global information on genetic resources and crop cultivars. This includes germplasm pedigrees, field evaluations, genetic (quantitative trait locus [QTL]) maps, structural and functional genomics data (including links to external plant databases) and environmental GIS data. The GIS map link in this category provides access to various maps produced by IRRRI's GIS unit.
Training materials	The training materials category is the largest in the entire Knowledge Bank. Containing more than 450 files in 34 separate topic areas, the training materials category is a staging and collection area for all instructional materials used in IRRRI Training's conventional face-to-face instruction. PowerPoint presentations, handouts, brochures, and lesson plans make up the majority of the assets stored in this category. The content within each category is easily searched using the training material's search feature.

The Rice Knowledge Bank logo

The Knowledge Bank's logo represents a stylized chromosome in the shape of a K (for the K in knowledge; knowledge is empowering and it is IRRRI's mandate to empower farmers with the knowledge to grow rice more efficiently). The colors on the K are yellow and green. This represents the green associated with rice and science and the enlightenment (yellow representing the sun) that comes with knowledge.

The Rice Knowledge bank's audience

For IRRRI's internal audience at the institute level, scientists are using the Knowledge Bank to prepare materials for traditional courses. Rather than reinventing the wheel, they can search the Knowledge

Bank for their topic, see what has already been written or developed, then make any adjustments required to customize the material to their instructional context. When the course is complete, the material is then uploaded to the training materials area for use during the next training. This effort saves hours of preparation time for future courses and ensures that training messages are delivered consistently.

In this regard, numerous contributions to the training materials area are being made by IRRRI scientists and their partners, CAB International, the University of Queensland, and the Royal Agricultural College of Cirencester. In the *Rice Grain Quality* course section, students' feedback and input and instructor's comments concerning grain quality are captured, and stored, allowing them to be searched and accessed. The collection and transformation of this tacit knowledge into explicit knowledge are an-

other first step for IRRI and the CGIAR in true knowledge management.

For IRRI's external audience, a concept that has grown out of the Rice Knowledge Bank is DigitalExtension. DigitalExtension workshops are offered at IRRI for NGOs, national agricultural research and extension systems (NARES), farmers, and IRRI partners. The workshops focus on how to use the Rice Knowledge Bank to build rice knowledge capacity that allows participants to make more informed rice production decisions for themselves or their constituents. According to Anita V. Antonio of the Philippine Rice Research Institute:

The Rice Knowledge Bank will be a big help to our organization because it is very informative and will readily assist our extension workers in the field who are attending to the different problems of the rice farmers especially in the area of principles and practices of farm management.

As a vital component of the Rice Knowledge Bank's external audience, partners help disseminate Rice Knowledge Bank information by hosting in-country training opportunities, providing translation services for Rice Knowledge Bank content, and sharing resources through collaborative projects. Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), India, has traditionally been a testing ground for IRRI innovations and the Knowledge Bank was no exception. As the first partner, TNAU facilitated delivery of the Knowledge Bank's first eLearning course, *Rice Grain Quality*. According to Natarajan Venkatachalapathy, a participant in the Rice Grain Quality eLearning course from Thanjavur, Tamil Nadu State, southern India,

The Rice Grain Quality eLearning course allowed me to work at my own pace, at home, using my own time. It was designed for scientists, millers, consumers, and traders, and it improved my skills in rice quality, production, costing, and identifying quality characteristics. The course was easy to understand, interactive, and interesting. Not everyone has the money or time to travel for training. In my case, I was not comfortable leaving my family for 2-3 weeks to take training in another country. By learning online, I was able to work at my leisure, didn't have to travel, and could easily communicate with the course's instructors even though we were thousands of miles apart.

For another partner, Angiang University, located in the Mekong Delta region of Vietnam, the

Rice Knowledge Bank's ability to be delivered via CD-ROM is ideal as Angiang University has a state-of-the-art internal computer network but lacks good Internet connectivity. By placing the Knowledge Bank CD-ROM on the university's internal network, students can access the content as if they were directly connected to the Knowledge Bank via the Internet.

With regard to CD-ROM delivery, more than 200 copies of the Knowledge Bank have been distributed in 11 different countries. Since the Knowledge Bank will always be a work in progress with new content being added every day, any time a CD-ROM version is requested, it is produced at that moment, thanks to the Knowledge Bank's single-source publishing methodology. This ensures that partners using the CD-ROM version have the most up-to-date information possible.

Vietnamese translation of Rice Doctor provided by Angiang University.

Accomplishments and future direction

As with any innovation, the Knowledge Bank's continued success depends on its early adopters and the steady stream of content provided by its contributors. In its brief history, the Knowledge Bank has

- grown to include 20 reference guides, 2 decision support tools, 2 eLearning courses, 5 KnowledgeBytes, and more than 450 raw training materials;

- experienced over 1 million hits on its Internet site;
- successfully trained and graduated 25 participants from the CGIAR and various partners using the Knowledge Bank's two eLearning courses; and
- established the concept and physically trained 14 participants from Philippine research institutes regarding the Knowledge Bank in IRRI's first-ever DigitalExtension workshop.

The Knowledge Bank's future will be one in which

- The Knowledge Bank will become a coordinated effort on a CG-wide scale.
- Partnerships will continue to be strengthened and established to disseminate the Knowledge Bank's content and to ensure that its development is demand-, rather than supply-, driven.
- Assets are continuing to be built while expanding on other distance-learning methodologies to bring a 360-degree learning capacity (learning anytime, anywhere, no matter what the technological limitations) to IRRI training.

eLearning for Development

A Training@IRRI online course.

<http://www.knowledgebank.irri.org>

- **What is eLearning?**
- **Is eLearning as effective as face-to-face instruction?**
- **What are the economics of eLearning?**
- **What are the advantages of eLearning?**
- **How do you ensure the proper design and effectiveness of your eLearning?**

For more information, contact irri-training@cgiar.org or visit the eLearning for Development course at <http://www.knowledgebank.irri.org>